

FABRICATION OF TiAl MATRIX COMPOSITE SHEETS WITH CONTROLLED MICRO-LAMINATED ARCHITECTURE BY A SOLID-LIQUID REACTION

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ABSTRACT

A feasible method has been successfully developed to manufacture fully dense TiAl matrix composite sheets with unique multi-layered architecture by employing multi-step reaction annealing of the hot-pressed (TiB/Ti)-Al laminates. The TiAl matrix composites displayed a novel layered structure, composing of alternating layers of equiaxed γ -TiAl layer, fully lamellar α_2 -Ti₃Al/ γ -TiAl layer and TiB-rich layer which was actually TiB whisker stacking layer. It is worth pointing out that the multi-layered composites showed the enhanced high-temperature tensile properties, in particular for 750 °C, the yield strength (σ_y) was much higher than that of monolithic TiAl prepared by the reaction annealing of Ti-Al laminates. Consequently, the unique micro-laminated TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets have potential for light-weight high-temperature structural application.

1 INTRODUCTION

TiAl-based alloys are regarded as one of the most potential heat-resistant lightweight structural materials in the 21st century due to their attractive properties, such as high specific modulus and specific strength, low thermal expansion coefficient, excellent oxidation resistance, etc [1-3]. However, the intrinsic brittleness leads to the difficulty in deformation processing of TiAl-based alloys and thus it poses a huge challenge for sheet forming, which

greatly restricts their practical application [4-6]. It is rather imperative to explore the new forming technique for the production of the TiAl-based alloy sheets. Therefore, researchers have exploited elemental foil metallurgy technique [3, 7-9]: pure Ti and Al elemental foils with excellent plastic deformability are stacked to obtain Ti-Al laminates and the laminates are subsequently reaction annealed to produce monolithic γ -TiAl sheets. However, the relative density and mechanical properties of final monolithic TiAl are rather low; in particular, the high temperature strength cannot satisfy the requirement for aerospace applications.

In the present work, a modified foil metallurgy method was proposed: in-house fabricated TiB/Ti composite foils and pure Al foils were alternately stacked to obtain (TiB/Ti)-Al laminates. Reaction annealing was subsequently employed to make solid Ti and liquid Al completely react; meanwhile the appropriate pressure was applied to improve the density. This method could avoid the direct deformation of brittle TiAl billets and finally fully dense TiB-TiAl composite sheets with multi-layered structure could be achieved.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Thin commercial pure Al foils with thickness of 200 μ m and in-house fabricated 2 vol. % TiB/Ti composite sheets with the thickness of 200 μ m were cut into 50 mm \times 30 mm squares. They were etched by 10% HF and 10% NaOH solution, respectively, and ultrasonically cleaned in acetone and dried. Surface pre-treated Al and TiB/Ti sheets were alternately stacked to form a “sandwich”. The schematic illustration is showed in Figure 1. The hot-pressing at 500 $^{\circ}$ C for 1.5 h under 25 MPa in vacuum was employed to prepare well-bonded (TiB/Ti)-Al laminates. The laminates were annealed in a vacuum furnace as follows: i) initial annealing at 1200 $^{\circ}$ C for 10 min under 0.1 MPa to completely consume Al and obtain TiAl₃ phases and subsequent densification treatment in vacuum ($\sim 10^{-2}$ Pa) under 50 MPa at 1200 $^{\circ}$ C for 2 h to enclose the Kirkendall voids formed during the initial annealing process; ii) second annealing for composition homogenization at 1300 $^{\circ}$ C for 5 h; iii) final annealing at 1350 $^{\circ}$ C for 10 min in order to obtain layer-structured TiAl composite sheets.

Microstructure observation, chemical composition analysis and phase identification of the final micro-laminated TiB-TiAl composite sheets were carried out using optical microscopy (OM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM, FEI Quanta 200F) equipped with energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDX). All SEM images were taken in the back-scattered electrons (BSE) mode. In addition, X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used to identify different phases. All the samples are examined in the rolling direction (RD) – normal direction (ND) plane.

Mechanical properties of the final multi-layered TiB-TiAl composite sheets were evaluated by tensile testing at ambient and 750 $^{\circ}$ C. The tensile samples were cut parallel to the rolling direction using electrical discharge machining (EDM) and their surfaces were carefully polished to remove the machining traces. The cross-section of tensile samples was 2.5 mm \times 1.5 mm and the gauge length was 15mm. The tensile tests were carried out at room temperature and 750 $^{\circ}$ C with an Instron-1186 universal testing machine with the initial strain rate of 1.3×10^{-4} s⁻¹. The samples were mechanically polished using 00-grade silicon carbide papers to remove surface scratches prior to testing. Fracture surfaces of tensile specimens were examined using a scanning electron microscope.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of (TiB/Ti)-Al laminates (only 9 of 21 layers are visible.)

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure evolution during reaction annealing

The microstructure of the hot-pressed (TiB/Ti)-Al laminates was shown in Figure 2 (a). Obviously, the microstructure of annealed specimen consisted of two different contrast regions. According to the compositional data detected by EDX, the phases of the dark grey and grey regions in Figure 1(a) correspond to the reaction layer and unreacted Ti, respectively. As shown in Figure 2(b), the composition of the reaction layer contained 26.59 at. %Ti and 73.41 at. %Al, corresponding to the intermetallic compound $TiAl_3$ phase. Residual Al did not found, this meant that Al had been completely consumed. There were numerous pores formed in $TiAl_3$ layers and a few of gaps appeared because of the Kirkendall effect. This was in accordance with the previous results [10-11].

Figure 2: The microstructure and compositions of the hot-pressed (TiB/Ti)-Al laminates after initial annealing at 1200 °C for 10 min

(a) The typical microstructure; (b) chemical compositions of the reaction layer

Subsequently, the densification treatment was conducted at 1200 °C for 2 h in vacuum ($\sim 10^{-2}$ Pa) under 50 MPa. The corresponding microstructure was indicated in Figure 3 (a). During the densification treatment, the pores formed during the initial annealing were completely closed because of the volume shrinkage under pressure and fully dense multi-layered composites were achieved. According to the results examined by SEM/EDX shown in Figure 3(b), the multi-layered composites composed of six layers: TiB stacking layer, Ti_3Al , TiAl, $TiAl_2$, Ti_2Al_5 layers and a small number of residual pure Ti.

Figure 3: the microstructure of the annealed samples after the densification treatment

(a) BSE image of the microstructure; (b) the line scanning analysis

The representative microstructure of the samples after the homogenization annealing was shown in figure 4(a). According to the results of SEM/EDX, the grey layer and dark grey layer contained 59.39at.%Ti-40.61at.%Al and 75.91at.%Ti-24.19at.%Al, respectively, corresponding to TiAl and Ti₃Al phases. The dark rod-like phase was identified as TiB whisker. This implied TiB whiskers did not participate in any reaction and were completely retained. As shown in Figure 4(b), XRD patterns indicated the presence of the close-packed hexagonal Ti₃Al with DO₁₉ structure and the tetragonal L1₀ TiAl. The peaks of TiB were not detected due to the low volume fraction.

Figure 4: (a) the representative microstructure of the sample after the homogenization annealing; (b) the corresponding XRD patterns

Finally the samples were annealed at 1350 °C for 10 min and the microstructure was shown in Figure 5. The resulting TiB-TiAl composite sheets displayed a typical multi-layered structure consisting of three layers: TiB whisker stacking layer (labeled as TiB-rich layer, the thin dark), equiaxed γ -TiAl layer (the gray) and fully lamellar α_2 -Ti₃Al/ γ -TiAl layer (the dark gray). The formation of the multi-layered structure could be attributed to the composition gradient which was easily controlled by managing the diffusion of Ti and Al. The colony size of fully lamellar α_2/γ structure and equiaxed γ grains were averagely 80 µm and 20 µm, respectively, which were much finer than that prepared by the conventional casting technique, close to the grain size refined by cyclic heat treatment [12-14]. This meant that the formation of the multi-layered structure was in favor of the microstructure refinement. In addition, no visible voids were found. Thus it can be seen that a feasible method has successfully been developed to produce fully dense TiAl matrix composite sheets with unique multi-layered architecture.

Figure 6: (a) the representative optical images of the multi-layered TiB-TiAl composite prepared by reaction annealing; (b) the schematic illustration of the multi-layered structure consisting of alternating layers of fully lamellar α_2/γ layer, equiaxed γ layer and TiB-rich layer

3.2 Tensile properties

The tensile properties of multi-layered TiB-TiAl composite sheets tested at ambient temperature and 750 °C were shown in Figure 7(a). The ultimate tensile strength (σ_{UTS}), yield strength (σ_y) and total elongation at fracture (δ) of the sheets at ambient temperature were 209 MPa, 209MPa and 1.17 %, respectively. The overall fracture surface of the composite at room temperature (Fig. 7(b)) was very flat and had some large cleavage faces, indicating a typical brittle failure. As a result, a fracture process was relatively rapid and the strength of the multi-layered composite sheets was not fully exploited. However, the multi-layered composites indicated excellent high-temperature properties. At 750 °C, the σ_{UTS} , σ_y and δ rise to 341 MPa, 323 MPa and 3.9 %, respectively, higher than those of monolithic TiAl prepared by roll bonding and reaction annealing of Ti-Al laminates [2, 7].

With increasing testing temperature, the total elongation at fracture shows a sharp increase (Fig. 7(a)) owing to the activation of additional slip systems [15, 16], which approached the value of monolithic TiAl prepared by roll bonding and reaction underway annealing [2]. As shown in Figure 7(b)-(c), the observation of fracture surfaces showed the interlamellar and translamellar fracture in fully lamellar α_2/γ layer and the pull-out and breakage of TiB whisker within the TiB-rich layer, irrespective of test temperature. Whereas in the equiaxed γ layer the fracture surface showed a sharp distinction. At room temperature, the typical transgranular cleavage fracture was observed, while the intergranular fracture was a major failure mode at 750 °C. The detailed investigation of the strengthening mechanism and fracture mechanism of the layer-structured composites are a part of ongoing research.

Figure 7: the tensile properties and fracture surfaces of final multi-layered TiB-TiAl composites (a) the tensile properties at room temperature and 750 °C; the morphologies of the fracture surface at (b) room temperature and (c) 750 °C

CONCLUSIONS

TiB-TiAl composite sheets have been successfully prepared by employing a feasible processing method of hot pressing and subsequent reaction annealing. The density of the multi-layered composites is significantly improved by hot pressing in vacuum under 50 MPa at 1200 °C for 2 h. The TiB-TiAl composites display a novel layered structure, composing of alternating layers of equiaxed γ -TiAl layer, fully lamellar α_2 -Ti₃Al/ γ -TiAl layer and TiB-rich layer. The multi-layered composites show enhanced yield strength at 750 °C and the ductility is significantly improved in comparison with

that tested at ambient temperature. Therefore, the multi-layered TiB-TiAl composites show a potential application for high temperature structural components.

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